

Utilization Of ICT Tools In The Supervision Of Teaching And Learning Processes In Public Secondary Schools In Osun State, Nigeria

Felicia Bosede Bamire, PhD

Department of Educational Management

Faculty of Education

Obafemi Awolowo Universities, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

This paper assesses the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools in the supervision of teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The study discusses four key areas, which include the availability and accessibility of ICT tools for secondary schools' supervision of teaching and learning in Osun state, the extent of ICT usage by school supervisors, challenges faced by school supervisors in the effective integration of ICT into the school supervision of teaching and learning and its impact on teachers' performance and students' learning outcomes. The concepts of ICT tools as well as supervision of teaching and learning in secondary school were also explained. Despite the global shift toward digital oversight in education, many public secondary schools in Osun State still face significant challenges, including financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, insufficient training, resistance to change and technological adaptation, lack of technical support and maintenance, poor internet connectivity, and weak policy implementation. It was revealed that the potential of ICT tools in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of school supervision, remains underutilized due to persistent structural and institutional challenges. The paper therefore proffers way-forward by advocating for targeted investments, capacity building, and policy reforms to foster a more ICT-driven supervisory culture. It was concluded that integrating effectively the ICT tools into school supervision of teaching and learning is capable of enhancing teachers' performance and students' learning outcomes.

Keywords: Utilization, ICT Tools, Supervision, Integration, Teaching and Learning

INTRODUCTION

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into educational supervision has become a vital strategy for improving the quality and efficiency of secondary education globally. Tools such as digital record-keeping, email, video conferencing, online forms, and mobile applications provide school administrators with innovative means to monitor, evaluate, and support teaching and learning. In the 21st century, traditional supervision methods alone are no longer sufficient. As global educational standards evolve, the demand for ICT-enhanced supervision grows accordingly [1]. In Nigeria, particularly in Osun State, the National Policy on Education advocates ICT adoption in schools to bridge the digital divide between developed and developing nations [2]. However, the implementation remains inconsistent. In spite of the government efforts, ICT use in school supervision of instruction across Osun State remains uneven. While many administrators are familiar with basic ICT tools, its integration into supervision tasks- such as lesson monitoring and teacher evaluations- is minimal [3]. Manual and paper-based systems continue to dominate the administrative and supervisory processes in the school which negatively affect the

effectiveness of the processes and results into risk of data loss.

The absence of a clear, localized framework further contributes to inconsistent ICT adoption, despite national policy support [4]. Infrastructure issues- such as unreliable electricity, poor connectivity, and lack of hardware- particularly affect rural schools, while even urban areas struggle with technical support and maintenance. These systemic issues underscore the need for targeted interventions to bridge the digital divide and promote equitable access to ICT resources across Nigerian schools [5]. The study therefore discusses ICT tools availability and accessibility for supervision in Osun state public secondary schools; extent of ICT uses by school supervisors in teaching and learning supervision; impact of ICT-Based supervision on teaching and learning in public secondary schools. It also discusses challenges to ICT integration in school supervision, and strategies for effective ICT-Based supervision in Osun state public schools. The study therefore, proffer some recommendations and conclusion.

Integrating ICT and optimizing its potentials are among the major challenges facing the supervision of

instruction in secondary schools in Osun State. Principals always want to avoid direct involvement in tech-based supervision [6]. Many research studies such as Wordu (7) and Wukari (8) provide additional insights into the challenges of ICT utilisation in secondary school's supervision. For instance, it was found that while ICT tools are present in public senior secondary schools, their utilization for instructional delivery is inadequate due to limited supply and low teacher competence. Similarly, it was revealed that teachers' access to ICT materials and skills significantly enhance instructional delivery, highlighting the importance of both availability and competence. Moreover, Odetola (5) indicated that only about 35% of public secondary schools in Osun State have internet access, and less than 20% use any form of digital platform for staff evaluation or academic reporting. Where ICT tools are available, their use is typically restricted to word processing or record-keeping, with minimal emphasis on analytics, digital observation, or remote supervision. Nonetheless, initiatives by NGOs and education partners have introduced basic digital tools in some schools. The Osun State Ministry of Education has also offered limited training workshops, though these efforts are neither widespread nor sustained.

In summary, while ICT awareness among school supervisors in Osun State is growing, its practical application remains constrained by skill gaps, infrastructure deficits, weak institutional support, and poor policy execution despite the fact that ICT has the potential to equalize access to quality supervision, especially for resource-constrained rural schools. Indeed, ICT has changed the way we live, work and play. The value of ICT is endless [10] ICTs not only give the opportunity to have easy access to information from various sources, but also facilitate resource sharing between and among various organizations apart from improving the status of the institution. Strategic and sustained ICT integration is essential for advancing educational quality across the state. A comprehensive assessment of current ICT practices is necessary to identify gaps and develop effective, context-specific strategies for improving educational supervision through technology.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

For regional policymaking and educational development, the study on the use of ICT tools to supervise teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria, is quite pertinent. Integrating information and communication technology (ICT) tools into teaching and learning processes has become more and more important as Nigeria works to improve its educational system and bring it into line with international norms. This study will shed light on how well ICT tools are used in public secondary schools and how much they

improve educational quality, particularly in the areas of managing and supervising instructional activities.

First, the study's conclusions can aid stakeholders, educational administrators, and legislators in comprehending the potential and difficulties related to ICT use in the classroom. The study will help guide plans to improve the infrastructure, training, and support systems required for the effective use of technology in schools by highlighting the level of ICT integration in teaching and learning oversight. In order to properly utilize ICT resources to enhance instructional quality and overall school management, it will also highlight the necessity of focused professional development programmes for educators and school administrators.

Second, by identifying best practices in the use of ICT tools for supervision, the study is capable of promoting beneficial educational reforms. Evidence-based suggestions on how ICT might be maximized to produce a more dynamic, engaging, and successful learning environment will be possible if it is clear how these technologies affect student learning outcomes and the effectiveness of instruction. It will also help create a strong framework for ICT adoption in Osun State schools and beyond, making the advantages of technology more generally available, especially in underserved or rural areas.

In conclusion, this study is important because it would help increase teacher effectiveness, improve educational oversight, and promote student achievement by using ICT tools in creative ways. In order to promote sustainable educational growth in Osun State, Nigeria, this study would be a useful resource for future interventions that address the gaps in ICT utilization in education.

THE CONCEPT OF ICT IN SECONDARY SCHOOL EDUCATION

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in secondary school education refers to the use of digital tools and resources to support teaching, learning, and school management. ICT encompasses a wide range of technologies including computers, the internet, interactive whiteboards, educational software, and mobile devices, all of which are used to enhance educational delivery and access [11]. It is an umbrella term that includes any communication device or application, such as: radio, television, cellular phones, computer, and network hardware and software, satellite systems as well as the various services and applications associated with them, such as videoconferencing and distance learning. When such technologies are used for educational purposes, to support and improve the learning of students and to develop learning environments, ICT can be considered as a sub-field of Educational Technology. Effective instructional supervision and delivery,

requires that information communications technology be integrated into lecture delivery, students' assignment, continuous assessment, examination, and evaluation of students such as in computer-based Testing (CBT) and in scoring of answer sheets of large classes. However, Gama (10) listed ICT facilities that are expected to be readily available in schools for a successful teaching, learning, and administrative activities as include computers, internet, television, radio, cassette player and a radio set, fixed telephone set and mobile phone, video machine and a video tape, real of real projector, slide projector, photocopying machine, duplicating machine, scanner, opaque projector, Email, among others.

ICT has transformed education by facilitating access to information, improving communication, and enabling more interactive and learner-centered pedagogies. Tella (13) revealed that ICT can be used in secondary schools for Instructional delivery, Student learning and School administration. Jegede (14), also supported that ICT enhances the quality of teaching and learning by providing teachers and students with access to a vast array of resources and interactive content that can make learning more engaging and effective. Ajayi (15) affirmed that the integration of ICT into secondary education helps in developing students' digital literacy skills, which are essential in the 21st-century knowledge economy. It also encourages independent learning and critical thinking among students.

In Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Education has acknowledged the role of ICT in transforming education and has initiated various policies aimed at promoting ICT integration in schools. However, implementation has been inconsistent due to infrastructural and financial constraints [16]. Despite the potential of the use of ICT in Nigerian secondary schools, it still faces numerous challenges. These include inadequate infrastructure, irregular power supply, lack of trained personnel, limited access to computers and internet facilities, and poor maintenance culture [17].

The principals often lack the training and confidence to effectively integrate ICT into their supervisory roles in schools. Eze (18) noted that without proper training and support, the introduction of ICT in schools may not significantly improve educational outcomes despite the critical role being played by ICT in modern secondary school education in enhancing teaching and learning processes, promoting digital literacy, and improving administrative efficiency. Therefore, to fully realize its benefits in Nigeria, there is a need for substantial investment in infrastructure, personnel training, and policy implementation.

The Concept of Supervision of Teaching and Learning in Secondary Schools

Supervision of teaching and learning in secondary schools in Nigeria refers to the process of guiding, monitoring, and improving the instructional practices of teachers and the learning outcomes of students. It is a critical component of educational management that ensures the effective implementation of curriculum and enhancement of teaching quality. Supervision in the educational context is primarily aimed at fostering professional development among teachers, ensuring curriculum implementation, and improving students' academic performance [19]. School supervision involves both the administrative and instructional supervision. Instructional supervision is particularly concerned with overseeing the teaching and learning processes, with the aim to support teachers through observation, feedback, and capacity-building [20].

According to Okendu (21), effective supervision ensures that teachers are not only meeting curriculum standards but are also adopting pedagogical practices that cater to diverse student needs. The process includes classroom observation, evaluation of teaching materials, mentoring, workshops, and performance appraisal. The key components of supervision include a) monitoring which involves observing classroom instruction, reviewing lesson plans and teaching materials, tracking student progress and performance; b) guidance and support which also entails providing feedback to teachers, offering professional development opportunities, encouraging collaboration among staff; c) evaluation entails assessing the effectiveness of teaching methods, reviewing student learning outcomes, conducting appraisals of teacher performance and (d) improvement which also involves identifying areas for growth, supporting innovation and best practices and implementing strategies to enhance teaching and learning. Supervision also plays a supportive role in teaching and learning process by providing opportunities for teacher professional growth through in-service training and collaborative learning [22]. When properly implemented, it motivates teachers, enhances job satisfaction, and ultimately improves student achievement [23].

Supervision in Nigerian secondary schools is carried out by various actors including principals, vice principals, heads of departments, and external inspectors from the Ministry of Education. These supervisors are tasked with assessing lesson plans, monitoring students' progress, evaluating teacher performance, and ensuring compliance with educational policies [24].

The supervision of teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools is a vital mechanism for maintaining educational standards and promoting

continuous improvement. However, to be effective, supervision must be carried out by trained professionals using modern, participatory approaches that emphasize collaboration rather than fault-finding.

However, in spite of its importance, supervision in Nigeria faces several challenges which include inadequate funding, lack of training for supervisors, shortage of manpower, and the use of outdated supervisory methods [25, 26]. Many schools lack the infrastructure and human resources needed to implement regular and effective supervision.

Supervision of teaching and learning is crucial for maintaining and improving educational quality in secondary schools therefore, integrating information and communication technology (ICT) into it, has become imperative as it fosters teacher development, enhances student performance, and ensures that schools operate as dynamic centers of learning.

Beyond data collection, ICT supports timely communication, performance tracking, and early identification of academic or behavioural issues [27]. Tools like Microsoft Excel, WhatsApp, email, and Google Forms enhance accountability and transparency.

Availability and Accessibility ICT tools for Supervision in Osun State Public Schools

The availability and accessibility of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools in public secondary schools are foundational to their effective utilization in supervisory processes. In Osun State, however, the level of ICT provision for supervisory purposes remains insufficient and unevenly distributed across urban and rural schools.

Studies have consistently revealed that many public secondary schools in the state lack essential ICT infrastructure such as desktop computers, laptops, projectors, internet access, printers, and data management systems [5]. Where these tools are available, they are often outdated, poorly maintained, or not functioning, limiting their effectiveness in daily administrative and supervisory activities.

According to Olusegun (3), only a small percentage of public-school principals in Osun State reported regular access to internet services and digital tools for supervision, with rural schools being the most disadvantaged. This digital divide significantly hampers the ability of supervisors to collect and analyze academic data, monitor instructional delivery, and communicate effectively with teachers and education authorities.

Furthermore, Odunlami (6) found that even in schools where ICT tools are present, accessibility is often restricted due to shared use between administrative and instructional needs. In many

instances, school administrators have to compete with teachers and students for access to computer laboratories or digital devices, making it difficult to conduct routine supervisory tasks consistently. In terms of mobile technology, there has been modest progress. Some school heads and supervisors use smartphones and messaging platforms such as WhatsApp for communication, lesson plan review, and scheduling. However, these are often informal and not fully integrated into structured supervisory frameworks [4].

The limited accessibility to ICT resources is further exacerbated by poor electricity supply, lack of internet coverage in remote areas, and the absence of technical support for equipment maintenance. These infrastructural barriers create an environment where the use of ICT tools for supervision is seen as supplementary rather than integral to the educational management process.

In summary, while awareness of the importance of ICT tools in educational supervision is increasing in Osun State, the actual availability and accessibility of these tools in public secondary schools remain low. Addressing these gaps is essential for improving educational quality, accountability, and data-driven decision-making in the state's secondary education system.

Extent of ICT tools Use by School Supervisors in Teaching and Learning Supervision

The effective use of ICT tools in the supervision of teaching and learning activities is essential for improving educational outcomes and enhancing administrative efficiency in secondary schools. However, in Osun State, the extent to which school administrators and supervisors actively engage with ICT tools in their supervisory roles remains a matter of concern.

Research indicates that while ICT tools are available in some schools, they are often underutilized by administrators and supervisors for their intended purpose—monitoring classroom activities, assessing teaching quality, and managing school performance data. Olusegun (3) found that while a majority of school heads in Osun State are familiar with basic ICT applications such as email, Microsoft Office, and Excel, they do not fully integrate these tools into their supervision routines. For example, classroom observations, lesson plan reviews, and teacher evaluations are still largely carried out using manual methods, such as paper-based forms and face-to-face interactions, despite the potential of ICT tools to streamline these processes.

A study by Odetola (5) revealed that only about 30% of principals and school supervisors in Osun State used ICT tools for performance tracking and

academic reporting. The limited use of digital tools for real-time data collection, communication, and performance feedback significantly reduces the potential of ICT in enhancing school governance and instructional effectiveness. In the absence of structured, digital systems, feedback loops between teachers and administrators remain slow, and data analysis for informed decision-making is hindered. Also, Odetola (5) indicated that only about 35% of public secondary schools in Osun State have internet access, and less than 20% use any form of digital platform for staff evaluation or academic reporting.

One of the primary reasons for this underutilization is the lack of comprehensive training in the use of advanced ICT tools for supervisory functions. According to Ogunlade (27), many school administrators in Osun State have not been trained in the use of specialized school management software or other ICT tools that could improve their ability to monitor and assess teaching practices. As a result, while they may use ICT for basic administrative tasks, they do not leverage the full range of tools available to improve supervision and support.

Furthermore, the busy nature of school administration, coupled with a lack of time and resources, means that school heads and supervisors prioritize immediate concerns over long-term technology integration. Many school leaders often rely on ICT for communication (e.g., sending emails or using mobile apps like WhatsApp) rather than for systematic supervisory practices such as academic tracking or instructional support [28]. This limited use of ICT tools results in missed opportunities to provide more timely and effective oversight of teaching and learning activities.

Although, some degree of ICT tool utilization exists among school administrators in Osun State, its application remains narrow and focused mainly on basic administrative functions. There is a need for targeted professional development programmes to equip school Principals with the necessary skills to fully utilize ICT in the supervision of teaching and learning processes.

Impact of ICT-Based Supervision on Teaching and Learning in Public Secondary Schools

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the supervision of teaching and learning processes has the potential to positively influence both teaching performance and learning outcomes [28]. There is growing evidence that when utilized effectively, it is capable of enhancing the quality of education delivered in public secondary schools particularly Osun State. However, ICT tools are not universally integrated into supervisory practices despite its immeasurable benefits which include the following:

1. Improvement in Teaching Effectiveness

ICT-based supervision allows for more efficient monitoring of teaching practices, enabling school administrators to provide timely feedback to teachers. Studies by Odetola (5) revealed that principals who utilize ICT tools for supervision can track lesson delivery in real-time, assess teaching methodologies, and ensure that curricula are being followed. By using digital tools like learning management systems (LMS), video recordings, and performance tracking software, school leaders can easily identify areas where teachers may need professional development or support. This increased oversight contributes to improving teaching effectiveness by fostering an environment where teachers receive continuous feedback and professional guidance.

In addition, ICT tools allow supervisors to collect data on students' performance more systematically and analyze trends in students' achievement. By examining performance data over time, supervisors can identify weaknesses in teaching methods and make evidence-based decisions on how to improve instructional strategies [3]. In Osun State, a few schools that have integrated ICT-based supervision report significant improvements in teaching standards, as teachers are more accountable for their instructional quality due to constant monitoring.

2. Enhancement of Learning Outcomes

The use of ICT tools in the supervision process also has a direct impact on students' learning outcomes. With ICT-based supervision, school administrators are better positioned to identify and address gaps in teaching delivery, which ultimately benefits students. When teaching quality improves through digital feedback and support, students are more likely to receive a higher standard of instruction, leading to better learning outcomes [28]. Additionally, ICT tools enable teachers to incorporate interactive learning materials, such as multimedia presentations, online quizzes, and virtual learning environments, which can enhance students' engagement and understanding of the subject matter. Akinwumi (4) emphasize that ICT-based supervision creates a feedback loop where students benefit from improved instructional strategies that are informed by data. For instance, student assessments can be integrated into digital platforms, allowing teachers to track individual progress and adjust teaching methods accordingly. This personalized approach to learning ensures that students' unique needs are addressed, leading to more effective and inclusive learning experiences.

3. Data-Driven Decision Making

One of the most powerful advantages of ICT-based supervision is the ability to make data-driven decisions. In Osun State, schools that have adopted ICT tools for supervision can analyze students'

performance data, teacher effectiveness, and other educational metrics to make informed decisions about school management. Supervisors can use data dashboards to monitor classroom activities, track student progress, and evaluate the effectiveness of different teaching strategies [6]. This data-driven approach leads to more targeted interventions, ensuring that resources are allocated where they are most needed to improve both teaching and learning outcomes.

4. Collaboration and Professional Development

ICT tools also foster collaboration between teachers and supervisors, which further contributes to enhanced teaching and learning. Through online platforms such as email, chat groups, and video conferences, teachers can engage with their supervisors more regularly and share insights into their teaching practices. This open line of communication helps create a professional learning community where teachers can collaborate on instructional strategies, share resources, and seek guidance from school administrators. In Osun State, schools with robust ICT support systems report higher levels of collaboration, which in turn positively affects both teaching and student outcomes [4].

The use of ICT tools in the supervision of teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Osun State has the potential to significantly improve teaching performance and learning outcomes. By allowing for real-time monitoring, personalized feedback, and data-driven decision-making, ICT tools enable school administrators to provide more effective leadership and support for teachers. As ICT-based supervision becomes more widespread, the quality of teaching and students' performance is likely to improve, contributing to the overall development of the educational system in the state.

Challenges to ICT Integration in School Supervision in Osun State

Several challenges impede the effective integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools in educational supervision in public secondary schools in Osun State despite the fact that its potential is widely recognized. These barriers hinder school administrators and supervisors from fully capitalizing on the benefits that ICT can offer for improving teaching and learning processes. The following challenges are identified:

1. Infrastructural Deficiencies

One of the most significant challenges is inadequate ICT infrastructure. Many schools in Osun State face difficulties in accessing basic technological resources such as computers, projectors, and stable internet connections [5]. In many rural areas, schools struggle with power outages, insufficient electricity supply,

and inadequate computer hardware, which makes it difficult for administrators to integrate ICT into their daily supervisory routines. According to Akinwumi (4), over 60% of public schools in Osun State lack the necessary facilities to support the implementation of ICT-based supervisory practices.

2. Limited ICT Training for Administrators

Another key challenge is the limited ICT training provided to school administrators. While some principals may have basic computer literacy, they often lack the specialized knowledge required to effectively use advanced ICT tools for supervision [28]. Training programmes for school leaders tend to focus on basic administrative tasks rather than the application of ICT in academic supervision, data management, and performance evaluation. Without targeted professional development programmes, school heads remain underprepared to embrace the full spectrum of ICT tools available for efficient school management [5].

3. Resistance to Change and Technological Adaptation

Resistance to change among school administrators and staff also poses a significant barrier to ICT integration. According to Olusegun (3), many principals and teachers in Osun State view traditional methods of supervision—such as paper-based record-keeping and face-to-face observations—as more reliable and less time-consuming than ICT-based methods. There is a prevalent attitude that technology may not significantly enhance the quality of supervision, which leads to reluctance in adopting new tools. This resistance can be attributed to a lack of confidence in using technology, unfamiliarity with digital tools, and the perceived difficulty of shifting from traditional to digital processes [28].

4. Financial Constraints

Financial limitations also hinder the widespread integration of ICT tools in Osun State's secondary schools. Many public schools face budgetary constraints, which make it difficult to allocate sufficient funds for the procurement, installation, and maintenance of ICT resources. Akinwumi (4) highlighted that the lack of consistent government funding for ICT initiatives and professional development programmes further exacerbates the digital divide between schools in urban and rural areas. Without external funding or public-private partnerships, many schools are left with limited or outdated equipment, rendering the integration of ICT into supervisory practices impractical.

5. Lack of Technical Support and Maintenance

There is often a lack of technical support to maintain the equipment, even in schools that have access to ICT tools. Olusegun (3) pointed out that many schools do not have dedicated ICT technicians or

maintenance teams to ensure that the devices remain functional. Without proper maintenance and regular updates, the lifespan of ICT resources is shortened, and the tools become unusable. The absence of ongoing technical support thus exacerbates the challenges faced by schools in using ICT for administrative purposes.

6. Poor Internet Connectivity

Finally, poor internet connectivity in many areas of Osun State remains a significant obstacle to the integration of ICT in supervisory functions. According to Odetola (5), many schools experience intermittent or unreliable internet service, which limits the use of cloud-based platforms for data management, online communications, and remote supervision. This lack of stable internet access inhibits the ability of school administrators to effectively monitor teaching and learning activities, especially in real-time, and access online educational resources for professional development. Effective integration of ICT tools in the supervisory practices of public secondary schools in Osun State is hindered by a combination of infrastructural, financial, technical, and human resource challenges. Addressing these barriers requires coordinated efforts from local and state government agencies, school administrators, and other stakeholders to improve access to ICT tools, provide adequate training, and ensure sustainable funding for ICT initiatives.

Strategies for Effective ICT-Based Supervision in Osun State Public Schools

Given the challenges identified, the following strategies have been identified for enhancing the effective use of ICT tools in the supervision of teaching and learning processes in Osun State. These strategies aim to address both infrastructural issues and human resource development, creating a more conducive environment for ICT adoption and integration in school supervision.

1. Improved ICT Infrastructure and Resource Allocation

To facilitate the effective use of ICT tools in school supervision, it is crucial to improve the ICT infrastructure in public secondary schools. The state government, in collaboration with educational stakeholders, should allocate more funds for the procurement of modern ICT tools, including computers, projectors, interactive whiteboards, and reliable internet connections. As highlighted by Akinwumi (4), schools in Osun State, particularly in rural areas, often struggle with inadequate ICT resources, which limits the effectiveness of supervision. By ensuring that all schools, regardless of location, have access to the necessary infrastructure, supervisors can fully utilize digital tools for monitoring, feedback, and data analysis.

2. Capacity Building and Professional Development for Supervisors

A key strategy to enhance the use of ICT in school supervision is the provision of targeted training and professional development for school administrators. Many principals in Osun State lack the advanced ICT skills necessary to integrate technology effectively into their supervisory roles [5]. Therefore, the state education authority should organize regular workshops, seminars, and training programs to equip administrators with the skills required to use ICT tools such as school management systems, digital tracking platforms, and online communication tools. Additionally, mentoring and peer-support programs can help build a culture of technological proficiency among school leaders. ICTs today according to Eda (29) are a major factor, in shaping the new globe economy and producing rapid changes in society. For education to harvest the benefits of ICTs in learning, it is expedient that pre-service and in service teachers have residual knowledge, skills and competences.

3. Government and Private Sector Collaboration

Collaboration between the government and the private sector can play a significant role in enhancing the use of ICT tools in Osun State's public secondary schools. The government can work with technology companies, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders to provide affordable and accessible ICT tools for schools. Public-private partnerships (PPP) can help reduce the financial burden on schools and ensure that schools receive the latest technological resources and technical support. Additionally, companies in the tech industry can sponsor ICT training programs for teachers and school administrators to ensure that they remain updated on the latest educational technologies.

4. Establishment of Technical Support Units

To ensure that ICT tools remain operational and continue to meet the needs of administrators, it is essential to establish dedicated technical support units within schools. These units can provide timely maintenance, troubleshooting, and repairs for ICT equipment, preventing the disruption of educational activities due to technical issues [3]. The creation of school-based ICT support teams will also help reduce reliance on external technicians, ensuring that ICT tools remain functional for longer periods. Additionally, trained technicians can assist in the installation of new systems and ensure that updates are carried out regularly.

5. Integration of ICT into School Policies

For ICT to be successfully integrated into supervisory practices, it must be embedded within the educational policies of the state. The education policy of Osun State should prioritize ICT integration as a key component of school management and supervision. By making ICT use mandatory in the supervisory

process, and by incorporating it into school development plans, the state can set clear expectations for administrators and educators. Furthermore, establishing clear guidelines on the use of ICT in education—such as acceptable digital communication protocols, data protection policies, and the integration of e-learning tools into teaching—can guide the effective deployment of technology in the classroom [28].

6. Encouraging a Culture of Continuous Learning and Innovation

A crucial strategy for enhancing the use of ICT tools in school supervision is fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation within schools. Teachers and administrators should be encouraged to regularly explore new technologies, teaching methods, and learning tools. This can be achieved by creating opportunities for professional development, facilitating access to online courses and resources, and encouraging collaboration among teachers to share best practices in the use of ICT for teaching and learning. As Olusegun (3) suggests, a culture of innovation will ensure that ICT tools are used not only to monitor performance but also to continuously enhance the quality of education.

7. Encouraging Student Involvement in ICT Usage

Students, as the primary beneficiaries of educational supervision, should also be involved in the integration of ICT tools. In schools where ICT is used effectively for teaching, students are often more engaged and motivated to learn. Supervisors can encourage the use of ICT tools in the classroom, such as online learning platforms, interactive apps, and digital assignments, to foster a more dynamic and participatory learning environment. By involving students in ICT activities, schools can create a technologically literate generation that is well-prepared for the demands of the 21st-century workforce. Therefore, enhancing the effective use of ICT tools in the supervision of teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Osun State requires a multifaceted approach. By improving infrastructure, providing adequate training, fostering partnerships, and integrating ICT into school policies, stakeholders can ensure that ICT tools become a regular and efficient part of school supervision. These strategies will not only improve administrative efficiency but also contribute to the overall improvement of teaching quality and students' outcomes, ultimately advancing the educational system in Osun State.

CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

1. **Increasing Knowledge of ICT Use in Educational Supervision:** The study provides a thorough analysis of the use of ICT tools in the oversight of public secondary school teaching and learning processes. It offers important insights into the real practices and

effects of technology in education management by concentrating on both the advantages and disadvantages of ICT integration. By emphasizing the subtleties of ICT adoption in the supervisory role which are frequently disregarded in more general research on ICT use in education this article adds to the body of knowledge already in existence.

2. **Identifying Barriers and Opportunities for Improvement:** The study advances knowledge of the obstacles to efficient ICT use, including inadequate technical assistance, a lack of teacher preparation, and restricted infrastructure. It also points out areas that could use development, like the possibility of focused training initiatives, improved facilities, and legislative adjustments that would make it easier to incorporate ICT technologies into the classroom. These results can assist school leaders, educational administrators, and legislators in identifying the critical areas that need to be addressed in order to improve the use of technology in the classroom.

3. **Offering a Framework for ICT Policy and Implementation:** Based on the study, a framework for ICT tool policy and implementation in public schools, especially in Osun State, can be developed. It offers doable suggestions for improving the supervision of teaching and learning procedures through the use of ICT resources. A methodical approach to ICT adoption that takes infrastructure and human capital requirements into account can be fostered by this contribution, which can influence educational strategies not just in Osun State but also in other Nigerian states and African nations facing comparable difficulties.

4. **Adding to the Body of information on ICT and Educational results:** The study adds to the body of information on how technology can improve educational results by investigating the connection between ICT tools and the oversight of instructional strategies. It adds to the continuing discussion on how technology might be used to enhance education in underdeveloped nations by highlighting the importance of ICT in raising teaching effectiveness, increasing student engagement, and encouraging creative teaching approaches.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance the utilization of ICT tools in the supervision of teaching and learning processes in Osun State's public secondary schools, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Capacity Building:** Government should organize regular training programmes for principals and educational administrators to improve their ICT competencies, focusing on practical applications in school supervision.

2. **Infrastructure Development:** Government should invest in the provision of essential ICT infrastructure, including reliable internet connectivity, computers, and power supply solutions, to facilitate seamless integration of ICT in school supervision.

3. Policy Implementation: Stakeholders should develop and enforce policies that mandate the use of ICT tools in supervisory practices, ensuring accountability and consistency across schools.

4. Resource Allocation: Allocation of adequate funding for the maintenance and upgrading of ICT facilities should be paramount as well as ensuring their sustainability and effectiveness in supporting educational supervision.

5. Monitoring and Evaluation: The stakeholders should establish mechanisms to regularly assess the effectiveness of ICT integration into school supervision, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation to emerging technologies.

CONCLUSION

The effective utilization of ICT tools in the supervision of teaching and learning processes in enhancing educational outcomes in Osun State's public secondary schools cannot be overemphasized. By addressing the existing challenges and implementing the recommended strategies, educational stakeholders can harness the full potential of ICT to foster a more efficient, transparent, and accountable supervisory system.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings from the study might not be immediately transferable to other parts of Nigeria or other nations with various educational environments because it focuses on public secondary schools in Osun State. The results may be impacted by regional differences in the socioeconomic circumstances, infrastructure, and ICT tool availability.

The study may have trouble accurately reflecting the diversity of Osun State's schools, depending on the number of schools and survey respondents. The study's capacity to make generalizations regarding the general efficacy of ICT use in school supervision may be restricted if the sample is not sufficiently large or diversified.

Depending on variables including finance, teacher preparation, and resource availability, there could be notable variations in the level of ICT adoption among schools. Since schools with more sophisticated ICT infrastructure can report better results than those with less access, this variance could introduce biases and make it challenging to evaluate the overall efficacy of ICT tools throughout the state. Self-reporting may be biased because the study depends on reports from educators, school officials, and other staff members. Also, respondents may underreport difficulties or overstate how well ICT tools are used in monitoring teaching and learning in secondary schools as they may want to portray the school's efforts in a favourable manner.

REFERENCES

1. Adu, F. A., & Olatundun, S. O. Digital Supervision Tools and Their Impact on Secondary School Management in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 13(2), 59–68. (2021).
2. Federal Republic of Nigeria. National Policy on Education (6th ed.). Lagos: NERDC Press. (2014).
3. Olusegun, O. B. Principals' Information and Communication Technology Literacy and Digital Tracking of Secondary School Activities in Osun State. *Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Pedagogy*, 1(2), 202–216. (2023).
4. Akinwumi, F. S., Faremi, S. J., & Olatunbosun, Y. O. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the Service of Administration and Supervision in Nigerian Public Schools. *Nigerian Journal of Social Work Education*, 19, 31–45. (2020).
5. Odetola, C. A., & Akomolafe, T. O. ICT Readiness and Utilization among Public Secondary Schools in Osun State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Leadership*, 5(1), 44–58. (2022).
6. Odunlami, A. A., Oyetunji, J. W., & Osuala, O. R. Assessment of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Usage by Educational Administrators of Public Secondary Schools in Osun State. *Journal of Education Innovation and Practice*. (2023).
7. Wordu, H., Oshebor, P. E., & Woke, G. A. Teachers' Perceptions on the Utilization of Information and Communication Technology for Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *International Journal of Modern Innovations and Knowledge*, 4(2), 45–56. (2023).
8. Ekunke, T. O., & Adewumi, I. B. Teachers' ICT Skills and Utilization of ICT Materials for Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Wukari, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research in Developing Areas*, 5(2), 224–236. (2024).
9. Abiogu, G. C. & Enemuo, P. C. Nigeria Teacher Education Reform: Implications for National Development. In O. A. Enoh (Ed.), *Educational Reforms in Nigeria: A Reader*. Saniez Publishers, Jos. (2007).
10. Gama, U. G. Application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Facilities to Reference and Information Service (RIS) Provision in University Libraries in North West Zone of Nigeria. *Information Impact: Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 3(1), 1–17. (2013).

11. Yusuf, M. O. Information and communication technology and education: Analysing the Nigerian national policy for information technology. *International Education Journal*, 6(3), 316–321. (2005).
12. Mondal, A. & Mete, J. ICT in Higher Education: Opportunities and Challenges. *Bhatter College Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(1). (2012).
13. Tella, A., Tella, A., Toyobo, O. M., Adika, L. O., & Adeyinka, A. A. An assessment of secondary school teachers' uses of ICTs: Implications for further development of ICT's use in Nigerian secondary schools. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 6(3), 5–17. (2007).
14. Jegede, P. O. Assessment of Nigerian teacher educators' ICT training. *Issues in Informing Science and Information Technology*, 6, 415–420. (2009).
15. Ajayi, I. A. Towards effective use of information and communication technology for teaching in Nigerian colleges of education. *Asian Journal of Information Technology*, 7(5), 210-214. (2008).
16. Ogunleye, A. O. Towards a successful implementation of ICT in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Educational Media and Technology*, 14(1), 23–29. (2010).
17. Aduwa-Ogiegbaen, S. E., & Iyamu, E. O. S. Using information and communication technology in secondary schools in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *Educational Technology & Society*, 8(1), 104–112. (2005).
18. Eze, P. I., & Uzoechina, G. O. Information and communication technology competence and use in teaching among secondary school teachers in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Technology*, 1(1), 84–92. (2015).
19. Adeleke, A. Educational supervision and quality assurance in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Educational Studies*, 15(2), 112-121. (2020)
20. Ezeocha, P. A. *Educational Administration and Planning*. Enugu: Optimal Computer Solutions Ltd. (1990).
21. Okendu, J. N. The impact of instructional supervision on academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Educational Research International*, 1(3), 68-73. (2012).
22. Nwaogu, J. I. *A guide to effective supervision of instruction in Nigerian schools*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers. (1980).
23. Adenaike, A. A., & Adebajo, A. T. The role of supervision in enhancing teachers' productivity in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 11(1), 34-42. (2017).
24. Onoyase, D. An evaluation of the role of school supervisors in enhancing teaching and learning in Nigeria. *African Research Review*, 8(1), 147-161. (2014).
25. Ukeje, B. O. *Educational Administration*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers. (1991).
26. Ijaiya, N. Y. S. Educational supervision and effective teaching and learning. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 11(1), 12-19. (1991).
27. Ogunlade, J. O., & Olanipekun, I. A. The Role of ICT in Enhancing Supervisory Practices in Nigerian Public Schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(5), 789–804. (2020).
28. Olowo, B. F., Adelokun, A., Akinola, B. O., & Subair, T. S. Information Communication and Technology Skills: A Veritable Tool for Principals' Administrative Effectiveness in Osun State Secondary Schools, Nigeria. *Journal of ELT Research*, 6(1), 77–90. (2022).
29. Eda, Y. ICT's role in curriculum integration, instructional delivery, and educational support. *International Journal of Educational Technology, Electronic Journal of e-Learning, Journal of ICT in Education*. (2011).